

Cultural Identity and Resilience through Song: Hakka Narratives in the Performance of Gongguan Mu Yu

Qijian Wu

College of Music, Mahasarakham University, Thailand

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3602-0740>

Sarawut Choatchamrat

College of Music, Mahasarakham University, Thailand

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9689-2477>

***Sayam Chuangprakhon**

College of Music, Mahasarakham University, Thailand

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5124-2953>

Wang Guangguo

Yancheng Teachers University, China

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4181-0426>

***Corresponding author email:** sayam.c@msu.ac.th

Abstract

Background: Gongguan Mu Yu is a traditional narrative folk song form performed in the Hakka dialect "Ya Hua," and it is anchored in the everyday life of Gongguan Town, Hepu County, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region of China. Music, particularly in traditional societies, serves not only as entertainment but also as a powerful vehicle for expressing identity and cultural memory.

Objective: This study investigates the performance of Gongguan Mu Yu as a cultural practice that expresses Hakka identity and supports community resilience in the Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China.

Methodology: This research adopts a qualitative ethnographic design, incorporating participant observation, in-depth interviews, and thematic content analysis of performances. This approach enabled the researchers to describe Gongguan Mu Yu and uncover its embedded meaning through lived community interactions.

Results: The performance of Gongguan Mu Yu embeds the song form within the community's historical, social, and cultural context, enabling a resonant portrayal of emotions that is enhanced by the Hakka dialect and its relatability to shared experiences. It is utilised in ritual and socio-recreational activities, demonstrating adaptation to modern realities through digital media promotion and youth involvement. Its successful preservation stems from a combination of both local administrative structures and grassroots initiatives.

Conclusion: Gongguan Mu Yu exemplifies a living historical practice that connects the past with the present, evolving in tandem with the community's social changes while fundamentally preserving its cultural identity.

Unique Contribution: This study highlights Gongguan Mu Yu's capacity to survive and evolve through community-driven innovation and social embedding, offering new insights into how musical heritage functions as a resilient force within minority ethnic cultures.

Key Recommendations: Future efforts should focus on the instructive role of Mu Yu and its potential integration into the local curriculum, its promotion on digital platforms, and formalising the informal, gendered documentation of teaching roles.

Keywords: Hakka folk music, cultural identity, community resilience, Gongguan Mu Yu, ethnomusicology

Introduction

Music is a universal form of human expression that transcends language and geography. As both sound and symbol, music is a powerful tool for communication, emotional expression, and the reinforcement of individual and collective identities. In traditional communities, music embodies memory, values, and lived experiences. In the strategically located and ethnically diverse environment of southern China's Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, the Hakka community has uniquely maintained its identity through its profound oral history, language, and music (Guangguo et al., 2024; Shun & Boonsrianun, 2023). Gongguan Mu Yu is one of the most remarkable manifestations of this identity, aka folklore, with a narrative traditional folk solo singing style where songs and music are customised while telling stories, 'Mu Yu' passed down from one generation to another. Located in Gongguan Town, Hepu County, Mu Yu is not only a genre of music but also an ethnographic monument of the Hakka people's past (Howard, 2016; McConaghy, 2020). These songs reflect impressions of life, genealogy, romantic stories and didactic poems all strung together through harmony and soaring speech. Mu Yu also brings along the language and cultural words important to the people from the Hakka community who sing the song in the Hakka dialect. It represents language and culture that are crucial to the identity of the singers (Lianzi et al., 2024; Luo, 2017). As a performative art and oral literature, it strengthens the Hakka people's sense of identity, cohesion, and continuity.

Traditional songs, especially in ethnic minority cultures, symbolise historical memory and social values. They function as expressive forms and tools of cultural continuity, resistance, and

adaptation across generations. Traditional art forms such as Gongguan Mu Yu face immense difficulties due to urbanisation, the rise of digital media, and changing lifestyles. Popular culture captivates the youth and diminishes the pace of folk traditions, overshadowing narrative-driven activities. Younger generations appear to be increasingly distant from the cultures of their ancestors. Comparable styles of music have sadly already disappeared in many areas of China. However, in Gongguan, Mu Yu is still alive, having been transformed to fit modern standards, with new life breathed into it through local festivals, and backed by efforts to preserve the culture (Addaquay, 2025; Howard, 2016). This is the reason why Mu Yu is so captivating. It raises the important question: what social mechanisms enable it to survive and thrive in contemporary society? What social, cultural, and performative frameworks allow it to resonate in an ever-changing community?

Therefore, this study examines Gongguan Mu Yu as a performance tradition and a resilient cultural mechanism that adapts and endures through social transformation. This study aims to investigate how Gongguan Mu Yu's performance functions as a cultural practice that expresses and sustains Hakka identity and community resilience in Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China. Guided by the question "How does the performance of Gongguan Mu Yu express and sustain Hakka cultural identity and community resilience in Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China?", the study utilises qualitative ethnography to investigate the connection between music and meaning.

This research outlines how Mu Yu reflects and reinforces the collective emotions, social sentiments, and social solidarity of the Hakka people through fieldwork in Gongguan Town, where the ethnographer conducted interviews and observations of performances and analysed lyrics. Moreover, it looks deeper into the genre's value regarding its transmission across generations, adjustments to social change, and its role as resistance or emotive expression.

This research is significant in the discourse on intangible cultural heritage, identity, and resilience. The preservation of folk music is frequently understood in terms of archival or museological lines. This study aims to clarify the impact of expression as a living cultural phenomenon. Through the testimony of Hakka performers and community members, the research demonstrates how traditional art can be curative. This meant that art could help one navigate different realities and even aspire to a different existence. While doing so, the study encroaches on areas of musicology, anthropology, and cultural studies (Morgan & Pink, 2018). This research defended the idea that local music traditions could be documented, studied, and sustained during times of accelerated societal transformation.

Literature Review

It has been noted that folk music is not simply a creative call but a living storehouse of language, recollection, beliefs and even social identity. Take, for instance, the Hakka folk songs. For them, folk music is not purely aesthetic artistry but also an emblem of identity. Within this framework, Gongguan Mu Yu stands out as a uniquely vivid example, offering musical narration of daily life in a deeply emotive and culturally multilayered manner. The researchers consider ethnomusicology, cultural identity, and community resilience theories to grasp why they remain

relevant to their people. Each one offers a distinct lens to comprehend the value of Mu Yu as a cultural expression amid ongoing societal shifts.

Music as Cultural Expression and Memory

Ethnomusicology scholars view music as a cultural practice deeply intertwined with a person's memory, identity, and existence. Furthermore, music is considered memory. It is a historical relic from the past that represents the echoes and values of a particular era. Folk songs from the countryside or those considered less important serve as folk chronicles, capturing the essence of local history, calling attention to moral values, or commemorating certain occasions. A song encapsulated in regional narrating dialects, Mu Yu captures the experience and understanding of a specific place of emergence and their community about how they relate to the world. Gongguan Mu Yu is a quintessential example of how the Hakka dialect, which serves as a marker of cultural identity, is articulated (Lidskog, 2016; Meng & Liu, 2023). The tales in Mu Yu fortify the memories of the people from where they came and the battles they waged against the challenges life threw their way, and reinforce the worldview shared among them.

Cultural Identity and Performance in Marginalised Communities

Cultural identity theory emphasises that identity is a representation of the self that undergoes significant transformations and can be expressed through symbols, rituals, and actions. Gongguan Mu Yu is a piece performed during Hakka ceremonial events. It constructs the identity of the Hakka people who form part of the intra-Chinese Diaspora. It enables the construction and/or reconstruction of an identity centred on preserving Hakka culture, language, and traditions. Although there are increasing external impacts, Mu Yu's work still shows that identity is flexible when put on stage and affirmed by a group. Hakka identity is not fixed, but rather, through these voices and actions, it is performed, enacted, and solidified, demonstrating its constant evolution (Leo, 2015; Lin, 2017; Wood & Homolja, 2021).

Community Resilience and the Adaptation of Tradition

The community's capacity to change while retaining its core identity completely encapsulates the concept of resilience theory. In this sense, Gongguan Mu Yu is not merely a relic of the past, but a strategy for coping with the present. Its features in festivals, educational, and local media suggest that, while still retaining some aspects of the old, it has transformed to cater to the needs of a modern audience. Change and adaptability without essence loss demonstrate cultural resilience. There is evidence of more structure in performance than in informal rural settings. If rhythm is moving to the digital era, then surely adaptability is resonating with Gongguan Mu Yu. Unlike the other folk traditions, which seem to have borne the brunt of urbanisation and globalisation, innovation is responding to the challenges with Gongguan Mu Yu. The younger generation takes the stage adorned with contemporary arrangements and hybrid themes, all signs of a living tradition trying to avoid fading away. Disassociated forces, such as community members, people local to the area, and local cultural policies, wield considerable scope for creativity in suppressing these actions. Noting the preservation efforts of a given structure gives one the impression that a person is resilient; however, true resilience comes from adopting a crafty approach to transforming whatever is being preserved (Chan, 2018; Holtorf, 2018; Mohammed & Sharif, 2024).

Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative ethnographic design, incorporating participant observation, in-depth interviews, and thematic content analysis of performances. The methodology is rooted in cultural studies and ethnomusicology, aiming to uncover meaning through lived community interactions and contextual performance settings (Beng, 2015; Curran & Radhakrishnan, 2021). The study was based in Gongguan Town, Hepu County, the centre of Hakka narrative song culture. Through active observation and participation, ethnography facilitated the most robust understanding of how myriad traditions are negotiated, performed, and lived.

Participant Observation

This study relied heavily on participant observation. The researcher studied several Gongguan Mu Yu performances in social and ritual contexts, including rural weddings, community festivals, and public heritage events. From observing the performers and the audience, and during the various interactions, the researcher perceived the Mu Yu tradition as a performative and constructive cultural practice. It showed how songs are not merely sung but lived and shared within daily life and the rhythm of seasons. Written field notes of people's gestures, expressions, and other comments recorded animated responses, which made it possible to appreciate the social and emotional aspects of the performance.

Intensive Interviews and Collection of Archival Information

Three extensive interviews were conducted with the selected key stakeholders to gain a deeper understanding of the conservation and performance of Gongguan Mu Yu. The first interviewee, a community arts leader, possessed a profound understanding and insight into the transmission of knowledge across generations and was quite helpful in illustrating how Mu Yu has been utilised as a tool for identity assertion, emotional expression, and event recall. The second interviewee, a local composer and administrator, possessed extensive knowledge concerning the tradition's evolution over time and the various musical characteristics associated with it. The third interviewee, a cultural historian, presented the roots of Hakka folk traditions from the region with considerable skill. Their insights were crucial in developing interpretations of Mu Yu's preservation strategies. The researcher conducted archival research at the Hepu County Cultural Centre and Beihai Mass Art Museum, retrieving documents that contained photographs, audio recordings, and scripts of earlier performances, which aided the researcher in obtaining materials for her interpretations.

Data Coding and Thematic Analysis

The researcher undertook manual thematic coding of the data, which included identifying motifs and patterns of interpretation. This analysis paid close attention to the words, style, imagery, and cultural construction of the roles of the performers and the audience. Significant focus was placed on how the Mu Yu songs express community values, moral lessons, and reactions to social changes. In performances and interviews, themes such as migration, family, hardship, gratitude, and cultural pride were prevalent. The analysis was organised thematically according to the study's main objectives, ensuring each theme aligned with the research questions. This helped answer the central research puzzle by demonstrating how Mu Gong Yuan functions as a cultural repository and a means of cultural resilience for the Hakka people.

Figure 1. Research Methodologies in Cultural Studies

This methodological design ensured that the research remained grounded in lived experience, cultural nuance, and the oral tradition of Hakka musical expression. Through this immersive approach, the study illuminated how Gongguan Mu Yu is performed and how it continues to foster a sense of rootedness and resilience in the hearts of its community.

Results

The results of this study are presented according to the research objectives, focusing on three major themes: 1) preservation and expression of Hakka language through Mu Yu; 2) ritual performance and communal identity; and 3) adaptation and resilience in changing sociocultural contexts.

Preservation and Expression of the Hakka Language

Performer's identity, community bonds, social status, and a sea of multicultural art styles are best represented in their native language. During the fieldwork, I observed a local Hakka dialect very clearly: "Ya Hua" is not an accent or a way of pronouncing words; it is a style of articulation which superficially conveys the spirit of Gongguan Mu Yu. The performance employs metaphoric and prosodic expressiveness, which is characteristic of the Hakka people of Guangxi. Respondents remembered and felt a sense of belonging and attachment to the vitality of the Hakka "Ya Hua". People shared how even a few sentences of Mu Yu brought back unforgettable recollections of a grandmother singing in the kitchen, communal joyful activities, or things heard as children.

The power of this phenomenon stems from its ability to evoke a sense of continuity. Hearing Mu Yu sung in Hakka, the endangered regional language, is given new life, serving as a multicultural reaffirmation and resistance. It makes them reminisce about their memories. To some elders, this

dialect serves as a living reminder of what once was, a way of remembering the past. For a younger audience who does not speak the language fluently, the songs reconnect them to their culture in a new and unfamiliar way, yet evoke a feeling of nostalgia.

West Side Story illustrates that the song serves as a reminder of home. The younger generation may not understand fully, but they can still feel connected to their culture. In this case, the youth can still feel the essence, even if they lack the capacity to express themselves with words. Accordingly, the linguistic scope of Mu Yu is an inseparable characteristic of their culture. The choice of words highlights the layered emotions, pauses, pitch shifts, and specific details work in unison to ensure the music traces back to the people's roots and cultivates their identity.

Ritual Performance and Communal Identity

Gongguan Mu Yu is not bound by stage or formal performances; it is, in its nature, a communal ritual. The research period encompassed performances in various contexts, ranging from official village functions to informal sessions beside a banyan tree. Without a doubt, Mu Yu's presence during life's pivotal moments, such as weddings, funerals, birthdays, and ancestral worship ceremonies, was most remarkable. These performances are not idle pastimes; instead, they are unifying social activities that actively bring individuals together.

For instance, specific wedding songs bless the couple, celebrate elders, and capture the poignant emotion of a daughter leaving her parental home. In this context, the Mu Yu songs appear more personal and are often tailored to the guests present at the ceremony, which is an improvisational event. The mood shifts at funerals: lyrics become more contemplative, sometimes even dealing with ancestry, venerating the life cycle, and paying homage to death. In both settings, Mu Yu captures the dynamics of emotions, becoming the vessel for celebration, sadness, pride, and reminiscence.

Besides having formal rituals, the songs are also performed in the fields, kitchens, and during breaks. The older women singularly seem to keep the tradition of singing Mu Yu alive while they weave, cook, and gather. The song Mu Yu aids in performing basic tasks, but more importantly, it establishes rhythm to daily activities, social relations, and oral traditions. One interviewee described it as "singing our stories while living them," highlighting Mu Yu's intimacy in people's lives. These performances represent important acts of preserving culture. They sustain rituals not through formal policies but through active engagement, emotion, and community spirit. As a song, Gongguan Mu Yu is a vivifying link between generations.

Adaptation and Resilience in Changing Sociocultural Contexts

Unlike other genres, Gongguan Mu Yu has much more to offer under the burden of tradition. Throughout the study, I was most struck by how flexible and adaptable the genre proved. With the onset of modernity, rural migration, and changing youth interests, Mu Yu caregivers have had to devise creative ways to sustain the tradition.

The latest work reflects modern-day ideas, including changes in the family system, the migration of younger family members from rural to urban areas, challenges within agricultural markets, and even the more lighthearted perspectives of internet culture. These changes hint at how responsive Mu Yu is to the world around it; it does not merely seek to preserve the past.

The performers' adaptation to new technologies has also influenced the art form. The performers upload and share their songs on sites like Douyin and WeChat, the Chinese version of TikTok. This helps reach younger audiences and enables Mu Yu to go far beyond the borders of Hepu County. The emotional essence and cultural sentiment embedded within the performances remain unchanged despite the differences in presentation, whether on a screen or beneath a tree in Gongguan.

Support from the community and the government has been instrumental. The formation of the Gongguan Mu Yu Art Troupe, an informal group of dancers who travel to perform at different functions and schools, has created an organised way to pass on the tradition. Furthermore, the integration of Mu Yu into the local school curricula has enabled a new generation of learners to appreciate the art, many of whom had some knowledge of the tradition's relevance but lacked a thorough understanding before these initiatives.

Tackling the challenges highlighted by interviewees, such as the availability of young people willing to learn the skill, is difficult, but at the same time, they remain optimistic. One elder recounted an experience in which a 14-year-old girl performed a newly composed Mu Yu about the pressures of school and pride in one's rural origins. "She did not just learn the form," he noted. "She made it her own. That is how we survive." These adaptations are more than simply preservation methods; they are expressions of cultural resilience. These inform us how a culture can change and respond to a shifting world while maintaining core values.

Discussion and conclusion

In our analysis, we cannot ignore the striking clarity of Gongguan Mu Yu, as it encapsulates a distinct form of song and captures the identity and spirit of the Hakka people of Guangxi. It was noted during the field work and interviews that the performance of Mu Yu features the Hakka dialect called "Ya Hua", marking it as one of the salient identificatory features of the community's speech and ethnicity. This finding concurs with those of Lianzi et al. (2024) and Meng and Liu (2023), who argue that local dialects within folk songs serve as potent markers of identity and heritage. The vibrant emotion from participants, regardless of age, when listening to Mu Yu performed in their dialect, illustrates music's powerful impact on constructing identity, consistent with the identity and music theory framework presented by Lidskog (2016).

Furthermore, the ritualised context of performing Mu Yu accentuates its preservation as a living archive. Unlike performing folklore in a set context, Mu Yu is integrated into the daily life of the people of Gongguan, sung at weddings, funerals, seasonal family gatherings, or even in casual, day-to-day contexts. This reaffirms Howard's (2016) definition of intangible cultural heritage as

“performative knowledge” and adds to the claim that community identity is jointly constructed by emblematic features such as music (Lin, 2017). The research methods, particularly participant observation, validated Curran and Radhakrishnan’s (2021) ethnographic approach by showing that these celebrations are richly emotionally charged, deeply participatory, and tailored to particular social settings.

The study also revealed that Gongguan Mu Yu demonstrates remarkable cultural resilience. Despite the onslaught of urban development, migration, and the global spread of mainstream culture, Mu Yu has not declined; instead, it has evolved. The experience of school stress, rural-urban migration, and even digital culture are incorporated in modern forms, which indicates how the tradition adapts while preserving its core structure. This strengthens Holtorf’s (2018) assertion that adaptability, rather than preservation, provides resilience to cultural heritage. Posting performance videos on Douyin and WeChat aligns with Chan’s (2018) assertion that innovation is essential for cultural sustainability, enabling a broader intergenerational reach.

In addition, the partnership among the local government, schools, and community art groups demonstrates the importance of both vertical and bottom-up approaches. The incorporation of Mu Yu into the school syllabus and its performance at public cultural events support Qin and Leung’s (2021) position on the necessity of heritage policy support. However, the study highlights that real preservation occurs in daily informal settings such as kitchens, community corners, and within intergenerational transmission led by women and elders.

Most notably, the inclusion of younger performers reinterpreting Mu Yu in their styles marks the creation of what may be called “living tradition.” For instance, a 14-year-old girl is composing a Mu Yu-style song depicting the modern academic rat race. She also illustrates how the next generation can breathe new life into cultural forms built on infusing current relevance into historical frameworks. This model counters the notion of tradition as something static or conservative, aligning with Mohammed and Sharif’s (2024) concept of hybrid culture as a transformative tool that remains rooted in core identities.

To summarise, Gongguan Mu Yu from Heping County exemplifies the dual role of traditional music as a cultural compass and a resilient instrument for intergenerational continuity. The research confirms that through language, ritual, creativity, and the passing down of traditions from elders to youth, Mu Yu has maintained a sense of Hakka identity amidst global transformations. Future research should explore the informal role of women in transmission processes, conduct cross-regional comparisons among Hakka communities, and examine the effectiveness of digital tools in youth music education. Adapting heritages while ensuring preservation is an untouched challenge that communities face, and Gongguan Mu Yu serves as a living example of how those challenges can be approached.

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